

India's Environmental Problem and Remedies

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DOI-

Abstract: The Indian environment has undergone a significant degradation in the last 50 years due to the rapid degradation of natural resources and the huge increase in pollution levels. Depletion of forests, population growth, vehicular emissions, use of hazardous chemicals, and various other undesirable human activities are mainly responsible for this deteriorating landscape of environmental health in India. In fact, it is causing considerable economic damage to the country and requires the utmost serious attention of the policymakers, administrators, scientists and people to save the environment and humanity and provide generational equality.

Keywords: Environmental Health, Global Issue, Greenhouse, Degradation, Protection Act.

Introduction:

India's achievement in science and technology during the last five decades appears to be very impressive which will reveal the expertise in built-in space research, nuclear engineering, steel production, fertilizers, petroleum, chemicals, machine tools, construction of large dams, etc. The miraculous achievement has been made in agricultural production during the last three decades through the Green Revolution, which transformed India in the fifties from an exporter to an importer of food grains. Technological progress in agriculture is made through the increase in production of new high-yielding varieties of crops through the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Undoubtedly, by bringing more land under food crops for the growing population, mankind has been saved from hunger and epidemics. On the other hand, various development activities like the construction of huge dams, and the setting up of power plants and industrial units have changed the human-nature relationship. They have changed not only the economic and socio-cultural life of the people but also their values, systems, ideas, beliefs, and indeed their entire lifestyle. The destruction of more forests for the expansion of land for agricultural purposes, for buildings, roads, and other constructions has led to the extinction of many plant and animal species and is also responsible for the ecological imbalance.

Environmental Problem and Global Issue:

India is not the only country facing environmental issues. Certainly, air and water pollution and climate change are more global issues that require a concerted effort by all countries to resolve. A report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change suggests that the world will experience so-called tipping points in ocean acidification, ice sheet melting, sea-level rise and climate impacts sooner than ever. Although environmental issues are global in nature, each country with jurisdiction over its territory is in control of its own environment and, therefore, must control, monitor and enact regulations to protect its environment. This is also true for India. The Copenhagen Agreement makes it clear that it is up to individual countries to formulate

and implement the necessary regulations to achieve their national commitments to combat global warming by reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Due to the specific role of the country in controlling and monitoring the environment, it is difficult to apply environmental standards to countries from a global perspective, each country must be prepared to consider and participate in environmental issues as a potential contributor to the overall global degradation of the environment. To control it by its laws and by the participation of its industrial sector. In addition, each country can be part of a global organization/organization that uses a global network, technical information, and resources that are the contributing partners of this group to help the environment. In particular, Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) collection and disposal is a major urban environmental problem facing India. India is not the only country with this problem, it seems that many developing countries and even some developed countries have to face MSW as an environmental concern. However, the disposal of MSW in India is a serious concern. Garbage collected by municipalities in India is dumped only outside urban centers. In addition, MSW releases methane and carbon dioxide which increases the effect of greenhouse gases. On environmental issues and concerns, India is overburdened as it is generally accepted that many developing countries have very high pollutant concentrations which leads to substantial costs for health and shorter life expectancy. Since the highest increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is projected to occur in developing countries such as China and India, these two countries are probably responsible for the future of this world. In the most recent available data, the amount of atmospheric particles in India is five times the concentration level in the United States and seven times the level of China in the US. Notably, in anticipation of the Paris Conference on Climate Change, which begins on November 30, countries are pledging how much they want to reduce emissions in the next few

decades. India and Brazil, perhaps the two most polluting countries in the world, are still committed to the Paris Conference.

Major Environmental Issues in India:

Rapidly growing population and economic growth are creating many environmental problems in India. The country's population is projected to grow to about 1.50 billion by 2030. The major environmental problem is deforestation and farmland, Depletion of Resources, Environmental Depletion, Public Health, Loss of Biodiversity, Security of Livelihood for the Poor, Population. The four basic demographic factors of birth, death, migration and migration cause changes in the size, composition, and distribution of the population, and these changes raise many important questions of cause and effect. Population growth and economic development are contributing to many serious environmental disasters in India. These include deforestation, deforestation, habitat loss, and loss of biodiversity. Energy needs have increased due to changing usage patterns. The end result is air pollution, global warming, climate change, water scarcity, and water pollution.

Degradation of Agriculture and Forest Land:

Approximately 60% of forest and farmland degradation is due to soil erosion, water logging, and salinity. It is estimated that between 5.8 and 14 billion tons of soil are destroyed each year by soil erosion. From 1987 to 2020, the average annual per capita water availability has dropped by about 75% to 2657 cubic meters, with groundwater over-exploitation being problematic in the states of Haryana, Punjab, and Uttar Pradesh. The Indian Institute of Agricultural Research estimates that a 5°C rise in temperature would result in a 20 to 25% loss in annual wheat production. For a country with such a large population, these are significant problems for those who depend on the productivity of primary resources and whose economic growth depends on industrial growth. Forests cover 20.54% of India's geographical area (698000 square km). Nearly half of the country's forest area is found in Madhya Pradesh (24.3%) and seven northeastern states (29.3%). The latter is experiencing net forest damage. Fuel timber harvesting and expansion of farmland are reducing forest cover. This trend, along with increasing industrial and motor vehicle pollution production, has led to an increase in atmospheric temperature, which is changing the nature of rainfall.

Type of Pollution:

Air Pollution:

Indian cities are polluted by emissions from vehicles and industries. Road dust from vehicles also contributes up to 33% to air pollution. In a city like Bangalore, about 50% of children suffer from asthma. The biggest cause of air pollution in India is the transport system. Excessive pollution was also

found to have an adverse effect on the Taj Mahal. Following the court's decision, all traffic in the area was shut down, and all industrial plants in the area were closed shortly thereafter. Air pollution in large cities is rising so much that it is now 2.3 times higher than the level recommended by the WHO. When it was decided to change its entire public transport system from diesel to compressed gas (CPG).

Water Pollution:

Water Pollution out of 3659 cities and towns in India, only 215 cities have partial treatment facilities and only 8 cities have complete wastewater treatment facilities. Used for drinking, bathing, and washing downstream, untreated water. This situation is characteristic of many rivers in India as well as in other developing countries.

Noise Pollution:

The Supreme Court of India passed a landmark judgment on noise pollution in 2005. Unnecessary horns of vehicles cause high decibel noise in cities. The use of loudspeakers for political purposes and through temples and mosques causes noise pollution in residential areas. The Government of India has recently introduced rules for permissible noise levels in urban and rural areas. How they will be monitored and implemented is not yet certain.

Land Pollution:

Land Pollution Land pollution in India is caused by pesticides and fertilizers as well as rust. In March 2009, the issue of uranium poisoning in Punjab came to light due to the fly ash ponds of thermal power stations, which caused severe congenital malformations in children in Faridkot and Bhatinda districts of Punjab, yet the British started deforestation in India. Since the partition of 1947, the pressure of modernization has only increased the rate of deforestation, which has deteriorated the soil, leading to land pollution.

Conservation of Biodiversity in India:

Biodiversity Conservation in India has significant biodiversity in the Indomalaya Ecozone. It is home to 8.3% of all mammals, 14.3% of avians, 7.3% of reptiles, and 6.6% of flowering plant species. In recent decades, human encroachment has become a threat to India's wildlife, in response to which the system of national parks and protected areas, first established in 1935, has been extensively expanded. In 1972, India enacted the Wildlife Conservation Act and Project Tiger to protect important habitats; The next federal defense was issued in the 1980s. With more than 510 wildlife sanctuaries, India now has 18 biosphere reserves, four of which are part of the global network of biosphere reserves. There are 28 wetlands registered under the Ramsar Convention.

Remedies on Environmental Problem:

Environmental Protection Act:

The Government of India has shown some foresight in the field of environmental concerns by enacting laws to protect the environment. India has about two hundred laws related to environmental protection. India's environmental regulations date back to the 1970s. The Water Act of 1974 and the Air Act of 1981 were the first important rules to be enacted. These laws created the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) responsible for data collection and policy implementation. It has also developed a detailed procedure for environmental compliance at the central government level. At the same time, another control board called State Pollution Control Board (CPCB) was set up at the state level to collect data and implement the policy at the state level. These other rules were followed to protect the environment. Objectives of the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 to provide protection and improvement of the environment. Making rules to control environmental pollution; Indicating standards and limits of air, water, and soil pollutants for various areas and purposes; Prohibitions and restrictions on the handling of hazardous substances, and the location of industries or fines may increase as long as anyone found to be responsible for the pollution can be liable to a fine of five lakh rupees to one lakh or both. (Sections 15, 16, 17) An additional Rs. 5,000 per day, however, can result in imprisonment for up to 7 years if not complied with for more than a year.

Forest and Wildlife Protection Act:

Forest and Wildlife Protection Act. 1927 - Indian Forest Act and Amendment 1984; 1972 - Wildlife Conservation Act Rules 1973 and Amendment 1991 1980 - Forest (Conservation) Act and Rules, 1981 Water 1882 - Accessibility Act. 1897 - Indian Fisheries Act. 1956 - River Board Act. 1970 - Merchant Shipping Act. 1974 - Water (Pollution Prevention and Control) Act. 1991 - Coastal Regulation Zone Notification.

Prevention of Air and Pollution Control Act:

Air (Pollution Prevention and Control) Act Factories Act and Amendments to 1987 1981 - Air (Pollution Prevention and Control) Act 1982 -Air (Pollution Prevention and Control) Rules 1982 - Atomic Energy Act 1987 - The Air (Pollution Prevention and Control) Amendment Act 1988-Motor vehicles.

Conclusion:

The rapid economic growth experienced by India is creating adverse and detrimental environmental conditions that are affecting the people of India as well as the wider global population. In the case of India, this is further exacerbated by the high population density and growth rate. Existing environmental laws, although covering a wide spectrum of environmental concerns, appear to be ineffective due to lack of implementation, lack of resources, and technical challenges facing a large

number of Indian companies, especially SMEs. In this scenario, India will have to adopt some sustainable measures which will address many issues facing the country, including environmental degradation, to sustain sustainable economic growth. Sustainable development, i.e., a prosperous economy and a healthy environment, which in many respects is the goal of diverse interests in the field of environmental issues, is important for the future of India and the world. Sustainable development means managing the various interests of a prosperous economy and at the same time maintaining a healthy environment.

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